

GEOLOGICAL AND MINERALOGICAL SCIENCES

GEOPHYSICAL MONITORING STUDIES OF GARNI SEISMIC POLYGON OF THE REPUBLIC OF ARMENIA

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Abstract

The paper considers geophysical monitoring observations on magnetic variations, on changes in the substance of subsoil radon on the territory of Garni Geophysical Observatory (GGO), on the seismic regime of the polygon, on the geochemistry of fresh spring water and water of mineral springs located in central Armenia (2010). The results of geophysical observations, the data of the chemical analysis of water, were compared with the seismic regime of the region and the accompanying geodynamic movements of the Earth's crust. In order to assess the stress-strain state of the Earth's crust in the seismically active region of Armenia, maps of isolines of equal values of deformation were developed according to the water levels of hydrogeodynamic boreholes in the region, reflecting the geodynamic movements of the Earth's crust in the form of local stress points (compression or tension).

Keywords: observatory, geophysics, monitoring, deformation, earthquake, epicenter, mineral spring, spring, magnetic module, radon.

Introduction

Geophysical monitoring of the Earth's crust was carried out at the Garni Geophysical Observatory in order to study and track the geodynamic processes of the Earth's crust. The study area is located in the central part of Armenia. Regional tectonic disturbances are represented by: Garni, Yerevan and Ararat-Sevan faults [1]. Groundwater of the study area belongs to the intermountain Ararat basin, which is an area of accumulation of underground runoff and includes large reserves of mineral water [2]. The monitoring observations were carried out on the geochemistry of mineral water: Bjni, Arzni, Azatavan, Vedi, Surenavan, a freshwater spring Gohar, located in the central part of the region of Armenia (Fig. 1) [3]. According to the chemical composition, the waters of mineral springs are classified as hydrocarbonate, hydrocarbonate-chloride, sodium and chloride-sodium. The total mineralization of waters is

from 3.6g/l-33g/l. Correlation analysis between the components of the chemical composition of the waters of the springs was carried out in order to identify the correlation coefficients between the components of the chemical composition of the waters of mineral springs and fresh springs. Correlation coefficients (R.) between total mineralization and carbon dioxide for Surenavan and Vedi mineral springs are the following $R_1 = 0.6$, $R_2 = 0.7$. Monitoring observations of variations in time of the absolute vector of the Earth's geomagnetic field (Δ) and changes in the composition of subsoil radon on the territory of the Garni Geophysical Observatory has been carried out.

Material

According to the seismic regime 43 earthquakes (Fig.1) took place 14 of which at the Ararat Seismic Polygon in Armenia during 2010.

Fig.1. The distribution of distribution of the number of earthquakes by months for 2010

As it is shown on the graph, the largest number of earthquakes occurred in the fifth month of this year, in the VI month there was not a single earthquake, and then the number of earthquakes decreased and the first

half of 2010 is characterized by increased seismicity. The graph of the distributions of hypocenters of occurred earthquakes, Fig.2 shows that the hypocenters of earthquakes were mainly located in 5-10 km depth.

Fig.2. Graph of hypocenters distribution of the earthquakes occurred in 2010

The seismicity map (Fig.3) is developed according to the earthquake catalog of data from digital seismic stations of the NSSS (National Seismic Protection Service) from $1.5 < M < 2.5$.

The map reflects the distribution of earthquake epicenters across the region, the largest accumulation of epicenters is observed at the Ararat seismic polygon and around it. In the northern part of the region earthquake epicenters are scattered along the Anatolian fault. When compared with the map of epicenters for 2009, the following is observed: in the central part of the region, the seismicity pattern is much discharged

and there were fewer earthquakes in the Garni seismic polygon in the current year than in the previous year. The number of earthquakes in 2010 increased in Lake Sevan and around. A lull in seismicity over the past years has been registered in the southern part of Armenia, perhaps due to an increase in seismic activity in nearby regions.

Results

The map of seismic energy in Fig.5, developed according to the values of seismic energy released in the sources of earthquakes that occurred in the study area for 2010.

Fig.5 Map of Seismic Energy

The map shows that the concentration of seismic energy sources is observed in the north of the region, at the Ararat seismic polygon, in the southern part of Lake Sevan and in the southwestern part of the Armenian border. The value of the total $\sum E$ seismic energy released in the earthquake sources in the study area in 2010 was $E=1.09 \cdot 10^9$ J, which is slightly lower than last year ($E=3.46 \cdot 10^9$ J). On 2.08.10, an earthquake of

$M= 2.6$ occurred in Garni, the hypocenter was at a depth of 8 km, the epicenter of the earthquake is located near the mineral spring Geghard.

Two days before the event, there was a change in the geochemistry of Geghard mineral water, in particular, a decrease in the value of silicic acid (H_4SiO_4) by 35 mg/l, an increase in CO_2 by 58 mg/l, and an iron (Fe)

content by 2.19 mg/l. According to the chemical composition of the Gohar freshwater spring which is located on the territory of the observatory, a decrease in SO_4 by 1.24 mg/l was revealed before the earthquake and a sharp recovery of the value to 6.17 mg/l after the event.

On the territory of the Garni Geophysical Observatory during the study period, monitoring measurements of the module of the full vector of the Earth's geomagnetic field were continued (ΔT) (Fig. 6).

Fig.6 Graph of the change in the total vector (ΔT) of the geomagnetic field of the Earth's geomagnetic field

Variations of the total vector of the Earth's geomagnetic field are impulsive. On the graph (Fig. 6), the arrow indicates the earthquakes that occurred during the study period which resulted in the disturbance of the

nature of the variations in the modulus of the total vector. The magnitude and form of the disturbance depends on the parameters of the earthquake, magnitude and epicentral distance.

Fig. 7 Changes in subsoil radon in the territory of the Garni Observatory for 2010

A graph (Fig. 7) has been developed based on measurements of subsoil radon in the territory of observatory which shows that the changes in the values of subsoil radon have an impulsive nature, and according to the received record, deviations from the background values with an increased amplitude of fluctuations are observed [4]. The dates of the earthquakes marked on the graph coincide with fluctuations in radon values with an amplitude above the background values. Thus,

the revealed effects according to the values of subsoil radon before earthquakes manifest themselves depending on the magnitude of the earthquake and the epicentral distance.

Monitoring observations were continued at the Garni Observatory at two geochemical profiles, on each of these profiles there are mineral springs: Surenavan, Ararat, Vedi; Arzni, Bjni; Geghard and fresh spring Gohar [5].

Fig.8. Changes in hydrogeochemical elements (CL, SO₄, Mg, HCO₃) at the profiles: a) min.source: Vedi, Ararat and Surenavan; b) Arzni, Bjni, Gegard, fresh spring Gohar.

As can be seen from the graph (Fig. 8a), the waters of the hydrogeochemical profile are characterized by an increased HCO₃ value, a sharp jump in the value of Mg is observed at the end of the profile, the graph (Fig. 8b), where the content of CL in the waters of the profiles is slightly increased at the beginning of the profile, and then goes on the decline, the waters of this profile are characterized by a low content of Mg and SO₄ at the beginning of the profile, and a decrease in their values towards the end of the profile. The resulting graphs reflect the distribution of hydrogeochemical elements

along the profiles for the entire period of monitoring observations. When comparing the obtained graph of changes in hydrogeochemical elements (Fig. 8b) with the graph of the previous year, an increase in the content of CL in the water of the Arzni mineral spring is observed.

The change in the values of total mineralization and carbon dioxide (CO₂) of the water of the Vedi mineral spring dissolved in water is shown in Fig. 9.

Fig.9 Graph of changes in total mineralization and carbon dioxide in the mineral water of the Vedi spring.

Earthquakes that occurred during the study period on the territory of the Ararat seismic polygon are marked on the graph. As can be seen from the figure, there are changes in the fluctuations in the values of total mineralization and CO₂.

The correlations between the parameters of hydrogeochemical effects and the characteristics of earth-

quakes have been studied [6]. The results of the correlation analysis showed that a statistically significant relationship between the parameters of the effects (effect time, extremum time) and the characteristics of seismic events (energy class, epicentral distance) was established for spasmodic, impulse and bay-like changes in the macrocomponent composition of groundwater (Table 1).

Table 1

Mineral Springs	Earthquake date	Earthquake parametre		Hydrogeochemical effect		Effect Types
		Epicent. dist □ (km)	Energetic class K	Extr. time	Effect time	
Surenavan	11.06.08	25	9,0	6,0	9,0	Bay-like
	18.06.09	54	11,4	3,0	6,0	Bay-like
Arzni	18.04.08	20	9,9	6,0	8,0	Impulse
	04.11.08	37	9,7	2,0	5,0	Impulse.
	18.06.09	20	11,4	4,0	7,0	Spasmodic
Bjni	03.10.08	12	8,3	3,0	5,0	Impulse
Vedi	4.11.08	54	9,8	3,0	6,0	Impulse.
Ararat	11.06.08	21	9,9	3,0	4,0	Spasmodic
Geghard	18.06.09	20	11,4	18	24	Impulse

According to the received data, it follows that the time of the effect and extremum of fast impulsive and spasmodic hydrogeochemical effects depend on the characteristics of seismic events (energy class-K, epicentral distance- Δ), and therefore reflect the processes developing at the stage of earthquake preparation.

A map of the values of deformations of the territory of Armenia [7] was developed based on the catalog of local earthquakes that occurred in 2010 (Fig. 10), Table 1.

Fig.10. Map of stress-strain state of Earth's crust of Armenia

◆ - mineral sources, ▲ - hydrogeochemical boreholes,
● - isolines of deformation, - - - active faults.

The map of the stress-strain state of the Earth's crust of Armenia reflects the distribution of deformation in seismically active areas of the Earth's crust in the region. The structure of deformation compression (concentrations of isolines of calculated deformation values) is formed in the central part and in the SW of the territory of Armenia. The structure of stretching and easing of the earth's crust tension is observed in the NW of Armenia (Fig. 10).

Conclusion

Based on the seismic regime of the territory of Armenia, 32% of the total number of earthquakes occurred at Garni polygon.

According to the results of geophysical monitoring, an increase in the geodynamic activity of the Earth's crust in Garni seismic polygon was revealed.

An increase in the activity of geodynamic processes in tectonic blocks: Yerevan and Yerevan-Ordubat has been observed, according to changes in the macrocomponent Cl, SO_4, HCO_3 and gas CO_2 composition of mineral and fresh waters.

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